

Signs of Possible High-Temperature Superconductivity in Graphite Intercalated with Lithium-Based Alloys

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Abstract: We report experimental results indicating possible high-temperature superconductivity in graphite intercalation compounds synthesized with lithium-based alloys. Temperature-dependent measurements of magnetization, trapped magnetic flux, and electrical resistance reveal transitions with critical temperatures (T_c) in the range of 240-350 K at ambient pressure, depending on intercalation metals and conditions. The highest T_c values and largest high- T_c fractions ($\lesssim 0.1$ %) were observed in graphite samples intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy. Our results and analyses suggest that the observed transitions originate from local superconductivity rather than intrinsic magnetic properties of the intercalated graphite, which may be an alternative explanation. Accordingly, we propose and intend to pursue further investigations to test and confirm the nature of the observed high- T_c transitions, and to obtain larger high- T_c fractions by optimizing the intercalation materials and methods.

Introduction

Theoretical predictions and recent experimental studies suggest that superconductivity at room temperature may be achievable in substances consisting of light elements.^[1-4] For example, high-temperature superconductivity at critical temperatures up to $T_c \approx 250$ K has been observed for hydrides at megabar pressures.^[5-7] Carbon-based materials are also considered as promising candidates for high-temperature superconductivity, because delocalized π -electron systems, low-dimensional frameworks, and high vibrational frequencies can enhance electron pairing and electron-phonon interactions.^[8]

The tuneable electronic properties of carbon allotropes such as graphite, graphene, fullerenes, nanotubes, etc. enable a variety of potentially superconducting phases. For example, superconductivity has been observed in boron-doped amorphous Q-carbon with $T_c \approx 55$ K^[9] and in $\text{Cs}_2\text{RbC}_{60}$ with $T_c \approx 33$ K.^[10] Superconducting transition temperatures above 100 K at ambient pressure have been predicted for C_{24} -network systems containing Na, Mg, Al, In, and Tl.^[11]

Signs of high-temperature superconductivity have been observed even in non-intercalated/undoped graphite, although these results remain controversial,^[12,13,14] and claims of superconductivity in graphite above room temperature have not yet been confirmed.^[15] Superconducting transitions below 0.5 K have been observed in rhombohedral tetra- and penta-layer graphene,^[16] while higher transition temperatures can be achieved in graphite intercalated with alkali or alkaline-earth metals and other species.^[17] For example, superconductivity with $T_c \approx 11.5$ K has been reported for CaC_6 ^[18] and $\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$ ^[19] and can be described by the BCS theory.^[20,21]

In a companion study, we obtained experimental evidence for possible superconductivity in graphite intercalated with calcium-ammonia solutions.^[22] In this study, we intercalated graphite with lithium-based alloys and observed signs of possible high-temperature superconductivity through independent and complementary measurements of magnetization and electrical resistance: 1) temperature-dependent magnetization in zero-field cooling (ZFC) and field cooling (FC) mode indicating expulsion of applied magnetic field below T_c (Meissner effect); 2) field-dependent magnetization characteristic for type II superconductors; 3) magnetic flux trapping and magnetic flux creep; 4) shift to lower temperatures and broadening of transitions with increasing magnetic field.

Results and Discussion

In the main text of this paper, we focus on three types of samples obtained by intercalation of expanded graphite sheets (SGL graphite) with melts of pure Li metal, binary Ca-Li alloy, and ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloys at temperatures in the range of 423 K to 623 K over a period of one to ten minutes as specified in Table 1. Details on the intercalation methods and complementary results obtained with other samples are presented in the Supporting Information (SI), including highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) and SGL graphite intercalated with other metals and alloys. The results obtained with HOPG

were qualitatively similar but less pronounced, which may be due to the high surface-to-volume ratio of SGL graphite^[23], which favors rapid diffusion and intercalation.

Table 1. Metals/alloys (molar ratios), reaction temperatures, and reaction times applied in the synthesis of the SGL graphite intercalation samples presented and discussed in the main text.

Sample name	Metal/Alloy (molar ratio)	Intercalation Temperature (K)	Intercalation Time (min)
Sample I	Li	623	1
Sample II	Ca-Li (1:3.5)	623	1
Sample IIIa	Sr-Ca-Li (1:1:20)	523	1
Sample IIIb	Sr-Ca-Li (1:2:20)	623	1
Sample IIIc	Sr-Ca-Li (1:2:20)	473	10
Sample IIId	Sr-Ca-Li (1:2:20)	423	10

Temperature-dependent magnetization

Figure 1 shows the temperature dependence of magnetization, $m(T)$, for SGL graphite intercalated with binary Ca-Li alloy (Sample II) measured in zero-field cooling (ZFC) and field-cooling (FC) mode. It reflects a well-established superconducting transition near 11.5 K, which can be attributed to a low-temperature superconducting phase of CaC_6 ^[18] or $\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$ ^[19] (low- T_c transition, Fig. 1a). A substantially smaller but still pronounced step in the ZFC signal indicates another transition at 240 K (high- T_c transition, Fig. 1b), which is consistent with similar high- T_c transitions observed in graphite samples intercalated with Ca-NH₃ solutions in the companion study.^[22] Decreasing the Ca content in Ca:Li alloy from 1:3.5 to a 1:20 resulted in a reduction of signal intensity for both transitions, while the high- T_c transition remained at about 240 K. Lowering the intercalation temperature to 523 K reduced the magnitude of the low- T_c transition and shifted the high- T_c transition up to 265 K (Fig. S12, SI). Overall, the samples obtained with binary Ca-Li alloys exhibited high- T_c transitions in the range of 240 K to 265 K (Fig. S13, SI). The ratio between high- T_c and low- T_c transition signals varied significantly with intercalation temperature, time, and proportion of Ca in the Ca-Li alloys, indicating that the high- T_c transition is not related to the low- T_c phase. The intercalation kinetics presented in the SI (Fig. S14) support this conclusion: longer intercalation times at temperatures above 623 K lead to a growth of low- T_c transition signal, while the high- T_c transition signal vanishes. Graphite samples intercalated with Li only (Sample I) did not show any high- T_c anomalies in magnetization measurements (Fig. S15, SI), which confirms that the observed high- T_c anomaly is due to intercalated Ca atoms in accordance with the result of our companion study^[22].

Figure 1. Temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of a graphite sample intercalated with binary Ca-Li alloy (Sample II) . a) low- T_c transition near 11.5 K attributable to known superconductivity in CaC_6 ^[18] or $\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$ ^[19], b) high- T_c transition near 240 K. Measurement data points from zero-field cooling (ZFC) and field-cooling (FC) modes (filled/ open circles); connecting lines to guide the eye.

Like calcium, strontium can form a SrC_6 phase with a significantly lower superconducting T_c of 1.65 K.^[24] In a graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIa), we did not observe a low- T_c superconducting transition above the experimental lower limit of 5 K (Fig. 2a). On the other hand, the co-intercalation with Sr increased the high- T_c transition temperature to 261 K. Apparently, co-intercalation with Sr suppresses the formation of the CaC_6 phase and may increase the amount of intercalated Ca in the graphite. Doubling the Ca content in the alloy and increasing the intercalation temperature raised the high- T_c transition temperature in Sample IIIb further to ≈ 270 K (Fig. 2b). Compared to binary Ca-Li alloys, graphite samples intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloys exhibited high- T_c transitions at higher temperatures up to 350 K (Fig. S16, SI). For instance, Sample IIIc exhibits a high- T_c transition near 350 K (Fig. 2c).

Figure 2. Temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of graphite samples intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloys (Samples IIIa, IIIb, IIIc): a) high- T_c transition at ≈ 261 K in Sample IIIa. b) high- T_c transition at ≈ 270 K in Sample IIIb (zoomed region displayed at top of panel). c) high- T_c transition near 350 K in Sample IIIc. Measurement data points from zero-field cooling (ZFC) and field-cooling (FC) modes (filled/open circles); connecting lines to guide the eye.

Trapped magnetic flux

The high- T_c transitions detected by temperature-dependent magnetization measurements may be attributable to magnetic or superconducting properties of the investigated samples. To elucidate the physical mechanism, we investigated the trapping of magnetic flux as an important hallmark of superconductivity^[25,26], which was effective in the probing of high-temperature superconductivity in hydrogen-rich compounds under high pressure^[27] and other superconductors at atmospheric pressure.^[28,29] The trapped magnetic flux occurs due to persistent currents in a superconducting sample after exposing it to a magnetic field. The induced magnetic moment, m_{trap} , decreases upon warming of the sample and disappears at T_c .

Figure 3b shows trapped flux measurements in graphite intercalated with a ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIb). The temperature dependence of the trapped magnetic moment, $m_{trap}(T)$, induced by application and subsequent switching of a magnetic field of 1 T at 5.2 K, shows a clear stepwise transition at approximately 270 K, which is in good agreement with the high- T_c transition temperature obtained in conventional temperature-dependent magnetization measurements of the same sample (Fig. 3a). The magnetization measured at reverse cooling from ≈ 286 K to 5 K is almost temperature-independent (run III, Fig. 3b).

Figure 3. Trapping of magnetic flux in graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIb): a) temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, measured in magnetic field of 6 mT perpendicular to carbon layers. Diamagnetic signal below 8.5 K attributed to concomitant low- T_c superconducting phase ($\text{CaC}_6/\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$).

b) Temperature dependence of trapped magnetic moment, $m_{trap}(T)$, measured in zero field. Trapped magnetic moment was generated at a magnetic field of 1 T at 5.2 K (ZFC protocol, H_M perpendicular to carbon layers). Strong increase of $m_{trap}(T)$ below 8.5 K attributed to trapped magnetic flux in concomitant low- T_c superconducting phase ($\text{CaC}_6/\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$). Black arrows indicate the course of temperature change in the experiment (runs I, II, III).

To check if induced magnetic moment could be of magnetic rather than superconducting origin, we also investigated the behaviour of $m_{trap}(T)$ in the trapped magnetic flux sample, which lost part of its induced magnetic moment upon heating to an intermediate temperature $T^* = 129$ K. When the temperature was again decreased below T^* (run I, Fig. 3b), $m_{trap}(T)$ remained essentially stable during a subsequent cooling and heating cycle in the range of 10 K – 129 K (intermediate plateau in Fig. 3b). When the temperature was further increased above $T^* = 129$ K (run II, Fig. 3b), m_{trap} follows the initial trajectory, ending with a step at $T_c \approx 270$ K. This observed behaviour suggests that the induced magnetic moment is due to superconductivity rather than intrinsic magnetism. If it were due to intrinsic magnetism, $m_{trap}(T)$ would not be expected to exhibit a stable plateau value during the cooling and heating cycle between 129 K and 10 K; instead, $m_{trap}(T)$ would be expected to follow the original heating curve or exhibit a similar temperature dependence with negative slope $\frac{\partial m_{trap}}{\partial T} < 0$.

The characteristic plateau of $m_{trap}(T)$ was first observed in trapped flux investigations of superconducting hydrogen-rich compounds under high pressure^[26] and was recently confirmed in superconducting Sn-Pb alloys at atmospheric pressure^[29]. In contrast, ferromagnetic materials usually

do not exhibit such characteristic plateaus with zero or positive slope as illustrated for weak ferromagnetic FeF₃ (Fig. S17, SI).

The slight, steady decrease in $m_{trap}(T)$ with $\frac{\partial m_{trap}}{\partial T} > 0$ observed upon cooling in the plateau region (Fig. 3b) can be attributed to the thermally activated creep of superconducting vortices, which according to the Anderson-Kim theory leads to a logarithmic decay over time of the trapped magnetic moment. Fig. 4 shows the decay of $m_{trap}(t)$ observed over a period of 20 hours for Sample IIIb in ZFC mode after application and switching off the magnetic field of $\mu_0 H_M = 1$ T at $T_M = 12.2$ K in two different orientations relative to the carbon layers. We fitted the measured $m_{trap}(t)$ data by an equation with logarithmic time dependence $m_{trap}(t) = m_{trap,0} - m_1 \times \ln(t)$ (green lines in Fig. 4), using $m_{trap,0}(12.2 \text{ K}) \approx 7.51 \times 10^{-9}$ A m² for $H_M \perp$ C-layers and $m_{trap,0}(12.2 \text{ K}) \approx 11.72 \times 10^{-9}$ A m² for $H_M \parallel$ C-layers, both estimated from $m_{trap}(T)$ trapped flux measurements. The rate of logarithmic relaxation $S = -\frac{1}{m_{trap,0}} \frac{dm_{trap}}{d \ln} = -\frac{k_B T}{U_{eff}}$ depends on the temperature and activation energy of motion of magnetic vortices U_{eff} . At $T = 12.2$ K relaxation rate $S(H_M \perp \text{ C-layers}) \approx -0.006$ and $S(H_M \parallel \text{ C-layers}) \approx -0.005$, whereas at higher temperatures its absolute value, as expected, increases: $S(H_M \perp \text{ C-layers}) \approx -0.007$ at $T = 130$ K and $S(H_M \perp \text{ C-layers}) \approx -0.013$ at $T = 260$ K.

Overall, the trapped flux experiments suggest that the observed high- T_c transition in the investigated samples is related to superconductivity rather than intrinsic magnetic phenomena.

Figure 4. Time dependence of trapped magnetic moment at $T = 12.2$ K, 130 K, and 260 K in graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIb). Trapped magnetic flux was created at $\mu_0 H_M = 1$ T and $T = 12.2$ K under ZFC protocol with two different orientations of the sample relative to the applied magnetic field (black circles): when H_M is parallel (upper panel) and perpendicular to carbon layers (lower panel). $m_{trap}(t)$ datasets were also measured at higher temperatures, $T = 130$ K (magenta circles) and $T = 260$ K (blue circles). For these measurements trapped flux were generated at $\mu_0 H_M = 1$ T, and $T = 130$ K and $T = 260$ K under ZFC protocol, respectively. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean value averaged over three independent measurements. Green curves are fits of experimental data by equation $m_{trap}(t) = m_0 - m_1 \times \ln(t)$.

Magnetic field dependence of high- T_c transition

To investigate the effect of magnetic fields on the observed high- T_c transition, we performed a series of $m(T)$ measurements in Sample IIIb at different magnetic field strengths and different orientations of the sample: parallel ($H \parallel$ C-layers) and perpendicular ($H \perp$ C-layers) to the carbon layers (Figs. 5a and 5b; Fig. S18, SI). With increasing magnetic field, T_c shifts to lower temperature, which is characteristic for superconductivity (Fig. 5c), and to a broadening of the transition, which is more pronounced when the magnetic field is parallel to the carbon layers, reflecting the higher inhomogeneity of the interlayer space compared to the carbon layers.

Figure 5. Magnetic field dependence of transitions in graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIb): temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, measured in ZFC and FC modes at different applied magnetic fields in two orientations: **a)** parallel to carbon layers; and **b)** perpendicular to carbon layers; dashed blue line marks high- T_c transition at zero field near 270 K. **c)** decrease of T_c with increasing magnetic field; T_c defined as intersection of two linear fits to the data across and above the transition (inset); dashed blue line is a fit based on the hyperbolic tangent function as specified in the SI (Sect. S.4.6, Fig. S20) **d)** change in magnetization $|\Delta m|$ during high- T_c transition as a function of magnetic field.

As illustrated in Fig. 5d, the change of magnetization during the high- T_c transition, $|\Delta m|$, exhibits a sharp initial increase and reaches a maximum at $\mu_0 H \approx 70 \text{ mT}$ ($H \parallel$ C-layers) and $\mu_0 H \approx 100 \text{ mT}$ ($H \perp$ C-layers), respectively. As the applied magnetic field is further increased, $|\Delta m|$ decreases continuously and finally disappears. The observed behaviour is characteristic for type-II superconductors and indicates a mixed state. The near-linear initial increase of $|\Delta m|$ resembles the virgin curve of magnetization due to the Meissner effect. Note that the behavior of $m(T)$ in the FC measurement of a Sample IIIb (Figs. 2b) and a Sample IIIc (Fig. 2c) also indicates a Meissner effect. The subsequent continuous decrease of $|\Delta m|$ is consistent with the penetration of vortices through the sample in a mixed superconducting state, thereby reducing the shielding of the applied magnetic fields by the Meissner state. The applied magnetic field at which $|\Delta m|$ reaches a maximum (Fig. 5d) can serve as an upper estimate for the penetration field H_p , above which the magnetic field begins to penetrate into a superconducting sample.

For fields parallel to the conducting layers, the shielding currents are more suppressed than for fields perpendicular to the planes, where the shielding currents flow within the homogeneous carbon layers. This leads to a lower first critical field H_{c1} in the parallel configuration and consequently to a lower penetration field value of 70 mT recorded in our experiment. For Sample IIIc with a high- T_c transition near 350 K, similar results were obtained as illustrated in Fig. S19 (SI) analogous to Fig. 5.

As shown in Fig. 5c, the decrease of T_c is exceptionally strong in relatively weak magnetic fields, whereas the field dependence of T_c weakens at higher magnetic fields. A magnetic field of 0.2 T reduces T_c by ≈ 15 K, corresponding to a slope of approx. 75 K/T, which is much more than expected according to known orbital decoupling mechanisms. For comparison, the high-temperature superconductor H_3S with $T_c \approx 203$ K exhibits a magnetic field effect decreasing the transition temperature by approx. 1.3 K/T.^[30] The unusually strong field dependence of T_c in the intercalated graphite may be related to Pauli paramagnetism of conducting electrons as reported for lithium-intercalated graphite,^[31] and their polarization in external magnetic fields. Due to strong background signals of the intercalation samples prepared with lithium alloys, we were not able to observe the characteristic signature of superconductivity in magnetic hysteresis measurements, which was achieved for the graphite samples intercalated with Ca-NH₃ solutions in our companion study.^[22]

High- T_c fraction in the intercalated graphite samples and resistivity

To determine the high- T_c fraction in the intercalated graphite samples, we performed magnetization measurements using a superconducting lead reference sample with the same dimensions. From the ratio of slopes at the near-linear initial increase of $|\Delta m|$ corresponding to the virgin curve of magnetization due to the Meissner effect as detailed in the SI, we estimated the high- T_c fraction f to be $\leq 0.1\%$ of the volume of the intercalated graphite samples. This estimate is based on the assumption that the high- T_c fraction is uniformly distributed throughout the sample.

As shown in Fig. 6a, the measurements in zero magnetic field of the graphite intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIId) do not exhibit substantial changes of resistivity at the high- T_c transition temperature near 350 K (Fig. S21), which can be attributed to the low abundance of the high- T_c fraction ($f \lesssim 10^{-3}$). Zero resistivity of the high- T_c fraction can be estimated to reduce the overall resistivity of the intercalated graphite sample by $f\rho \approx 0.1 \cdot 10^{-9} \Omega \text{ m}$, which is less than the average noise level $\approx 0.2 \cdot 10^{-9} \Omega \text{ m}$ of four-probe resistance measurements. Nevertheless, the conductivity of the Sample IIIId is several times higher than for non-superconducting graphite intercalated with Li metal only (Sample I), indicating higher density of conducting electrons as discussed below. Both resistivities exhibit a power-law temperature dependence up to approx. 100 K followed by a linear increase up to approx. 200 K, which is characteristic for metallic conductors. At higher temperatures, however, the resistivities exhibit a steeper increase deviating from the linear trend, which may be explained by increased charge carrier scattering due to the thermally activated motion of Li⁺ ions as detected by μ^+ SR in LiC₆ and LiC₁₂.^[32]

Up to 300 K, the differences between the resistivities of Sample IIIId measured in a magnetic field of 5 T and zero magnetic field were within the noise level of our resistivity measurements $\approx 0.2 \cdot 10^{-9} \Omega \text{ m}$ (Fig. 6b). A couple of spikes observed near 300 K and 330 K were slightly higher but still comparable to the noise level. At 350 K, however, the resistivity difference measured at 5 T was by a factor of 5 higher than the noise level. Its behaviour correlates with the high- T_c transition as indicated by the trapped flux behavior of Sample IIIId near 350 K (Fig. 6b). This observation can be plausibly explained if we assume that the magnetoresistance of the high- T_c fraction in the normal (non-superconducting) state is substantially higher than the magnetoresistance of the non-superconducting surrounding in the intercalated sample. We suggest and intend to further explore and elucidate this effect in follow-up studies with extended resistance measurements of intercalated graphite samples in variable magnetic fields.

The absence of pronounced resistivity changes at high T_c transitions in zero magnetic field does not contradict possible superconductivity if the high- T_c fraction is distributed in the form of isolated fragments or granules rather than in the form of interconnected filaments. Due to the low volume fraction ($f \lesssim 10^{-3}$), the average distance between compact granules would be over 10 times larger than their size.

Figure 6. Temperature-dependent resistivity and trapping of magnetic flux in graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample III d): **a)** Four-probe resistance measurements of graphite intercalated with pure Li metal (Sample I, black curve, right axis) and with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample III d), green curve at zero magnetic field; magenta curve at 5 T parallel to carbon layers; left axis) with increasing temperature. Inset shows correspondent resistivities in the upper range of temperatures. **b)** Difference between resistivities measured in magnetic field of 5 T and zero field (blue curve) and trapped magnetic flux (black curve) in Sample III d. Temperature dependence of trapped flux generated at 1 T and 5.2 K indicates high- T_c transition near 350 K.

Conclusions

At present, we cannot yet fully clarify the origin of the observed high- T_c transitions, but the available experimental evidence suggests that it may be granular or local superconductivity as previously reported for undoped Grafoil (microcrystalline graphite similar to SGL graphite) with a transition temperature of 14 K.^[33] Theoretical studies forecast that interfaces between rhombohedral graphite and hexagonal graphite (Bernal graphite) are especially promising for high- T_c superconductivity due to flat bands at the Fermi energy.^[34] X-ray powder diffraction and Raman spectroscopic measurements confirmed the presence of the hexagonal and rhombohedral phases of the SGL graphite used in our study (Fig. S3 and S4, SI). Moreover, an enhancement of conducting electron density is also expected to favour high- T_c superconductivity,^[34] and our resistance measurements indicate that the conducting electron densities in the high- T_c samples intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy are higher than in non-superconducting graphite intercalated with Li metal only.

Critically reviewing our results, we have also considered other alternative explanations, such as magnetic impurities, superparamagnetism, or other intrinsic magnetic properties of the intercalated graphite samples. However, the following features speak against an intrinsic magnetic nature and for a superconducting origin of the observed high- T_c transitions:

- i) temperature-dependence of magnetization weaker than expected for spin-glass or superparamagnetic behaviour (Fig. 5 a,b);
- ii) field-dependent magnetization consistent with type-II superconductors (Fig. 5d);
- iii) characteristic plateau in the temperature dependence of trapped magnetic moment (Fig. 3b).

Ongoing experiments show that the observed high- T_c transitions and signs of possible superconductivity are not limited to Ca-doped systems. Graphite samples intercalated by K-Li, Sr-Li, Mg-Li, Zn-Li, and Mg-Zn-Li alloys exhibit similar effects as presented in the SI (Fig. S23 – S25).

In summary, we present reproducible observations of high- T_c transitions suggesting possible superconductivity in SGL graphite intercalated with Li-based alloys at ambient pressure exhibiting T_c

values near and above room temperature. Further experimental and theoretical studies are required to independently confirm and further elucidate the observed phenomena.

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Data Availability Statements

Data will be published in suitable online repository.

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.^[35-41]

Keywords: superconductivity • room temperature • graphite intercalation compounds • Meissner effect • magnetic flux trapping

Author Contributions

M.I.E. initiated the study and developed it together with V.K. and V.S.M., who contributed equally to the overall research project. The samples were prepared by V.K with contributions from V.S.M. The measurements and analyses presented in this paper were performed by V.K. with contributions from V.S.M. V.K. and U.P. wrote the manuscript with contributions from V.S.M., M.I.E., and A.P.D. All authors discussed the results and conclusions.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

S.1 Measurement methods

S.1.1 Magnetic susceptibility measurements

Direct current (D.C.) magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed in a S700X SQUID magnetometer by Cryogenic Limited. Several small pieces of sample (length and width $\approx 2\text{-}3$ mm, thickness $\approx 0.1\text{-}2$ mm) with a total mass in the range of 5-30 mg were covered by anhydrous kerosene or silicone oil and put into a gelatine capsule (inner diameter ≈ 4 mm). Samples were predominantly oriented with carbon layers perpendicular to the applied magnetic field. For some measurements, samples were oriented with carbon layers parallel to the magnetic field.

The trapped magnetic flux was generated under zero field cooling (ZFC) and field cooling (FC) conditions. The typical ZFC protocol included cooling of the sample at zero field from $T > T_c$ to the target temperature below T_c . At the target temperature the magnetic field was applied for approximately 1 hour, then the applied magnetic field was gradually decreased to 0 T. In FC mode the sample was cooled from its normal state at the applied magnetic field to the target temperature below T_c , waiting for approximately 1 hour, and then the applied magnetic field was gradually decreased to 0 T. After removal of the applied magnetic field in both ZFC and FC modes the SQUID magnetometer was allowed to stand at 0 T for approximately 4 hours to let the system relax and minimize noise associated with jumps of the magnetic flux in the superconducting magnet of the SQUID magnetometer. The fields applied for magnetization ranged from 16 mT to 2 T. Successive $m_{\text{trap}}(T)$ measurements were performed upon warming of the sample with temperature steps of 1-3 K. Before each cycle of magnetization, the sample was converted to its normal metal state by warming the sample to $T > T_c$ at zero field, and the superconducting magnet of the SQUID magnetometer was degaussed to eliminate remnant fields.

S.1.2 Electrical resistance measurements

Four-probe resistance measurements were performed on bulk samples of rectangular shape. The samples were prepared and electrically connected using a special holder with gold-plated contact pins in a glovebox under Argon ($\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O} < 0.1$ ppm). A Si diode temperature sensor was placed close to the sample in quartz ampule filled with He exchange gas at atmospheric pressure. Excitation current from an AC resistance bridge (Model 372, Lake Shore) with amplitudes in the range of 33 μA – 1 mA at a frequency of 13 Hz were applied to ensure minimal heating of the sample with low heating power (approx. 0.1 nW). Measurements in zero field and magnetic fields were performed in the S700X SQUID magnetometer using the same AC resistance bridge.

S.1.3 Scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray analysis.

Scanning electron microscopy of pristine and intercalated graphite samples was done using a Ferra III Focus ion beam device (Tescan). The energy dispersive X-ray analysis was performed using the Oxford Instruments device integrated in Ferra III FIB.

S.1.4 X-ray powder diffraction.

X-ray diffraction data were collected at room temperature on a STOE Stadi P powder diffractometer (STOE&Cie GmbH Darmstadt), using $\text{MoK}\alpha_1$ radiation, Ge-(111) monochromator and a Dectris MYTHEN 1 K detector.

S.1.5 Raman spectroscopic characterization.

Raman spectroscopic measurements were performed at room temperature on bulk samples of HOPG and SGL graphite using a self-built Raman spectrometer equipped with a Newport N-LHP-928 HeNe laser with a wavelength of 632.817 nm the HORIBA / JOBIN YVON HR 460 spectrometer.^[35]

S.1.6 Measurement uncertainties/error estimates.

The S700X SQUID magnetometer allows to measure magnetic signals (total moment) with experimental errors of the order of 10^{-11} A m². In external magnetic fields up to 300 Oe (“set low field” option), the experimental noise of our installation is $\approx 1 \cdot 10^{-10}$ A m². At higher magnetic fields (“set field” option), especially in field range between 500 Oe – 1000 Oe the noise level was $\approx 2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ A m².

The experimental standard deviation of our four-probe resistivity measurements (Sample IIIId) using the AC resistance bridge with an excitation current of 1 mA was $\approx 0.2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ Ω m (determined at $T < 20$ K).

S.2 Starting materials

In the present study, we used two types of graphite for intercalation. Most experiments were performed with expanded graphite sheets SGL (purity $\geq 99,85\%$, SGL CARBON GmbH) with high specific volume^[22] and with the following chemical composition specified by the supplier:

Element	Content
Carbon	$\geq 99,85\%$
Ash content	$\leq 0,15\%$
Sulphur	< 300 ppm
Chlorides	≤ 10 ppm
Fluoride	≤ 10 ppm
Halogens	≤ 40 ppm

Additional experiments were performed with highly oriented pyrolytic graphite, HOPG (purity 99,99%, Magnametals). Energy dispersive X-ray analysis confirmed the high purity of both graphite starting materials (Figures S1 and S2).

Prior to intercalation, the graphite samples were annealed at 723 K for 2 hours in an Ar flow with H₂ (5%) to remove adsorbed gases and water. Untreated graphite samples were also tested but did not yield well reproducible results.

For intercalation, the following reactants were used: Ca (99.5%, redistilled, Alfa Aesar), Li (99.9%, Alfa Aesar), Sr (99.9%, Alfa Aesar), K (99.9%, Alfa Aesar), Mg (99.8%, Alfa Aesar), Zn (99.999%, Alfa Aesar), anhydrous silicone oil and kerosene both dried with metallic sodium in a Ar glovebox under Argon ($O_2/H_2O < 0.1$ ppm).

Figure S1. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis of HOPG. Top: scanning electron microscope image of the analyzed surface and maps showing the distribution of the determined elements. Bottom: EDX spectrum. The surface was cut parallel to carbon layers at a half of the thickness of the used material. The sample underwent the standard treatment prior the analysis: annealing at 723 K in Ar-H₂ flow (5% H₂) for 2 hours. The analysis confirmed high purity of the pristine graphite material.

Figure S2. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis of SGL graphite. Top: scanning electron microscope image of the analyzed surface and maps showing the distribution of the determined elements. Bottom: EDX spectrum with the zoomed area of interest, showing the peaks from impurity elements. The surface was cut parallel to carbon layers at a half of the thickness of the used material. The sample underwent the standard treatment prior the analysis: annealing at 723 K in Ar-H₂ flow (5% of H₂) for 2 hours. The analysis revealed impurities of phosphorus and sulfur (approx. 0.04 atomic percent each), likely from the technological process of compacting the expanded graphite.

The crystalline structure of HOPG is hexagonal, whereas SGL graphite shows coexistence of both hexagonal and rhombohedral phases in relative amounts of ~ 60% and ~ 40%, respectively, as determined by XRD measurements (Figure S3).

Figure S3. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) analysis. a) highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) and expanded graphite sheets (SGL graphite). b) HOPG diffraction patterns indicating hexagonal phase. c) SGL diffraction patterns indicating hexagonal (H) and rhombohedral phases (R) in amounts of $\sim 60\%$ and $\sim 40\%$, respectively.

Further structural characterization of pristine graphite samples was performed by Raman spectroscopy.

Figure S4. Raman spectra of HOPG (a,b) and SGL graphite (c,d). b),d) 2D peaks of HOPG and SGL graphite with Lorentzian line fit (I₁, I₂, I₃).

Figures S4 shows the Raman spectra of highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) and expanded graphite sheets (SGL graphite) with D and G bands at ~ 1332.0 cm⁻¹ and ~ 1585.0 cm⁻¹ for

HOPG and $\sim 1327.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1575.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for SGL graphite. The 2D band located at $\sim 2670.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for HOPG and $\sim 2679.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for SGL is the second-order overtone of the D band, alternatively also designated as D1 band.^[36] According to Latychevskaia et al.^[37], the linewidth of the 2D peak and its form are fingerprints of hexagonal and rhombohedral phases of graphite, and the stacking configuration can be determined from the ratio of Lorentzian subpeaks as shown in Figures S4b and S4d. The intensity ratio $R = I_3/I_2$ can be used to characterize the different stacking configurations in hexagonal and rhombohedral phases of graphite with $R > 1.7$ for ABA-stacking (hexagonal) and $R < 1.3$ for ABC stacking (rhombohedral)^[37]. We obtained $R = 1.8$ for HOPG and $R = 0.55$ for SGL graphite, confirming the hexagonal structure of HOPG and the simultaneous presence of hexagonal and rhombohedral phases in SGL graphite, which is consistent with the XRD results.

Four-probe resistance measurements of the SGL graphite show a temperature dependence similar to semiconductors (Figure S5).

Figure S5. Resistivity of SGL graphite sample.

S.3 Synthesis and characterization of intercalated samples

Calcium, strontium, magnesium and zinc readily form alloys with lithium, which remain liquid at temperatures well below the melting points of the pure alkaline-earth metals^[38-41] and can be used to intercalate graphite under well-controlled conditions. Intercalations were carried out in a stainless-steel crucible heated by a custom-designed miniature furnace under an inert argon atmosphere inside a glove box. Freshly cut pieces of the doping metal and lithium were weighed and placed in the crucible, then melted at temperatures ranging from 423 K to 723 K upon stirring to ensure a homogeneous alloy. The graphite samples were then immersed in the liquid alloy. The intercalation time was varied from 5 seconds to several days, after which the samples were removed from the melt and allowed to cool to room temperature. Prior to removal from the glove box, the prepared samples were covered by dried silicon oil or paraffin. At room temperature, the intercalated samples were stable as long protected from oxidants.

Importantly, the intercalation proceeded differently with different types of graphite. While the intercalation of HOPG samples required hours to days, SGL graphite can be efficiently intercalated in seconds to minutes, which may be due to the high surface-to-volume ratio of SGL graphite^[23], which favors rapid diffusion and intercalation. Thus, we mainly used SGL graphite in this study unless mentioned otherwise.

Figure S6 shows photographs of graphite samples intercalated with Ca–Li alloys. Electron micrographs and energy dispersive X-ray analyses of graphite intercalated with binary Li–Ca, Li–Sr and ternary Li–Ca–Sr alloys are presented in Figures S7 – S10.

We also explored intercalation of graphite with other binary and ternary alloys, including Sr–Li, K–Li, Mg–Li, Zn–Li, and Mg–Zn–Li alloys. The preparation of these alloys and the subsequent intercalation of graphite was done the same way as for Sr–Ca–Li alloys. For each sample, the intercalation temperature and time are specified in the figure caption. The energy dispersive X-ray analysis of the SGL graphite intercalated by binary Mg–Li alloy is presented in Figure S11.

Figure S6. Photos of graphite sample intercalated with Ca–Li (1:3.5) alloy at 623 K for four days. Intercalated SGL sample cut (a) perpendicular and (b) parallel to the carbon layers.

Figure S7. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis of the graphite intercalated with binary Ca–Li alloy. Top: scanning electron microscope image of the analyzed surface and colored maps showing the distribution of the determined elements. **Bottom:** EDX spectrum. The sample was synthesized by intercalation of graphite (HOPG) with Ca–Li (1:3.5) alloy at 623 K for 91 hours. The surface was cut parallel to carbon layers at a half of the thickness of the synthesized sample and covered by dry silicon oil. The analysis revealed the presence of doping Ca atoms intercalated into graphite. Ca content amounts approximately 9.9 atomic percent. The C:Ca:O ratio suggests the composition of $\text{CaC}_{4.2}$ and the derived Li:Ca atomic ratio of 3.0:1, assuming that Li and Ca were completely oxidized to Li_2O and CaO and the Si:O ratio in the used silicon oil is 1:1.

Figure S8. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis of the graphite intercalated with binary Sr–Li alloy. Top: scanning electron microscope image of the analyzed surface and colored maps showing the distribution of the determined elements. **Bottom:** EDX spectrum. The sample was synthesized by intercalation of graphite (SGL) with Sr–Li (1:3) alloy at 623 K for 1 minute. The surface was cut parallel to carbon layers at a half of the thickness of the synthesized sample. The analysis revealed the presence of doping Sr atoms intercalated into graphite. Sr content amounts approximately 6.1 atomic percent. The C:Sr:O ratio suggests the composition of $\text{SrC}_{8.6}$ and the derived Li:Sr atomic ratio of 11.4:1, assuming that Li and Sr were completely oxidized to Li_2O and SrO .

Figure S9. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis of the graphite intercalated with ternary Sr–Ca–Li alloy. **Top:** scanning electron microscope image of the analyzed surface and colored maps showing the distribution of the determined elements. **Bottom:** EDX spectrum. The sample was synthesized by intercalation of graphite (SGL) with Sr–Ca–Li (1:1:20) alloy at 523 K for 1 minute. The surface was cut parallel to carbon layers at a half of the thickness of the synthesized sample. The analysis revealed the presence of both doping Ca and Sr atoms intercalated into graphite. Ca and Sr content amounts approximately 2.7 and 2.1 atomic percent, respectively. The C:Ca:Sr:O ratio suggests the composition of $\text{Ca}_1\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{C}_{22.4}$ and the derived Sr:Ca:Li atomic ratio of 0.8:1:22.8, assuming that Li, Ca, and Sr were completely oxidized to Li_2O , CaO , and SrO .

Figure S10. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis of the graphite intercalated with ternary Sr–Ca–Li alloy. **Top:** scanning electron microscope image of the analyzed surface and colored maps showing the distribution of the determined elements. **Bottom:** EDX spectrum. The sample was synthesized by intercalation of graphite (SGL) with Sr–Ca–Li (1:1:20) alloy at 423 K for 1 minute. The surface was cut parallel to carbon layers at a half of the thickness of the synthesized sample. The analysis revealed the presence of both doping Ca and Sr atoms intercalated into graphite. Ca and Sr content amounts approximately 2.1 and 2.5 atomic percent, respectively.

The C:Ca:Sr:O ratio suggests the composition of $\text{Ca}_1\text{Sr}_{1.2}\text{C}_{31.6}$ and the derived Sr:Ca:Li atomic ratio of 1.2:1:22.6, assuming that Li, Ca, and Sr were completely oxidized to Li_2O , CaO , and SrO .

Figure S11. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis of the graphite intercalated by binary Mg–Li alloy. Top: scanning electron microscope image of the analyzed surface and colored maps showing the distribution of the determined elements. **Bottom:** EDX spectrum. The sample was synthesized by intercalation of graphite (SGL) with Mg–Li (1:4) alloy at 623 K for 5 minutes. The surface was cut parallel to carbon layers at a half of the thickness of the synthesized sample. The analysis revealed the presence of doping Mg atoms intercalated into graphite. Mg content amounts approximately 1.1 atomic percent. The C:Mg:O ratio suggests the composition of $\text{Mg}_1\text{C}_{55.5}$ and the derived Mg:Li atomic ratio of 1:72, assuming that Li and Mg were completely oxidized to Li_2O and MgO .

S.4 Results of magnetic measurements

S.4.1 Samples intercalated with binary Ca–Li alloys under different conditions

Figure S12(a,b) shows magnetization $m(T)$ measurements of the sample synthesized at 623 K within 1 minute using SGL graphite and a melt of binary Ca–Li alloy (atomic ratio 1:3.5, Sample II). It demonstrates well-established superconducting transition below 11.5 K (Fig. S12a) which could be attributed to CaC_6 ¹⁸ or $\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$ ¹⁹ low-temperature superconducting phases (hereinafter low- T_c). However, inspection of high temperature range indicates a small but pronounced step in $m(T)$ zero-field cooling (ZFC) run at ca. 240 K (hereinafter high- T_c transition) (Fig. S1b), which is not present in the field-cooling mode (FC). Note that Fig. S12(a,b) is also shown and discussed in the main text (Fig. 1a,b). Varying the synthesis conditions, we found that graphite samples intercalated by Ca–Li alloys at temperatures of 623 K and 723 K also exhibited low- T_c and high- T_c transitions. Decreasing the Ca content in Ca:Li alloy from 1:3.5 to a 1:20 resulted in a reduction of signal intensity for both transitions, while the high- T_c transition remained at about 240 K (Fig. S12 (c,d)). Lowering the intercalation

temperature to 523 K reduced the magnitude of the low- T_c transition and shifted the high- T_c transition to 265 K (Fig. S12 e,f).

Figure S12. Temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of graphite samples intercalated with binary Ca-Li alloys under different conditions. a,b sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:3.5) alloy at 623 K (1 min); a) low- T_c transition near 11.5 K attributable to known superconductivity in CaC_6 ^[17] or $\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$ ^[18], b) high- T_c transition near 240 K.. **c,d** sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:20) alloy at 623 K (1 min). **e,f** sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:20) alloy at 523 K (1 min); magnitude of low- T_c transition reduced and high- T_c transition shifted to 265 K. Measurement data points from zero-field cooling (ZFC) and field-cooling (FC) modes (filled/open circles); connecting lines to guide the eye.

Figure S13. Temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of graphite samples intercalated with binary Ca-Li alloys under different conditions. **a)** sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:3.5) alloy at 623 K for 10 minutes; high- T_c transition at ≈ 242 K. **b)** sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:20) alloy at 623 K for 30 seconds; high- T_c transition at ≈ 244 K. **c)** sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:50) alloy at 723 K for 15 seconds; high- T_c transition at ≈ 243 K. **d)** sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:20) alloy at 523 K for 60 seconds; high- T_c transition at ≈ 265 K. Applied magnetic fields were perpendicular to carbon layers in the samples. Measurement data points from zero-field cooling (ZFC) and field-cooling (FC) modes (filled/open circles); connecting lines to guide the eye.

Figure S14. Low- T_c and high- T_c transitions of graphite samples intercalated with binary Ca-Li alloys for different reaction times. Panels **a)** and **b)** show ZFC $m(T)$ data for sample synthesized with Ca-Li (1:3.5) alloy at 623 K with intercalation times from 10 seconds to 120 minutes. Panel **a)** shows low- T_c superconducting transition at $T_c \approx 9\text{--}11$ K; Panel **b)** shows high- T_c transition at $T_c \approx 240$ K. Panels **c)** and **d)** show the dependence of the observed magnetization change Δm at the superconducting transitions in the low- T_c (Panel **a)** and high- T_c (Panel **b)** transition versus intercalation time. Solid line represents the exponential fit of experimental data. Applied magnetic fields were perpendicular to carbon layers in samples.

S.4.2 Sample intercalated with lithium

Figure S15. Temperature dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of graphite sample intercalated with lithium only (Sample I, 623 K, 1 min). ZFC-FC measurements are done in different magnetic fields as indicated in the figure labels.

S.4.3 Samples intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloys

Figure S16. Magnetization $m(T)$ measurements of graphite samples intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloys. **a)** sample synthesized with Sr- Ca-Li (1:1:20) alloy at 523 K for 1 minute (Sample IIIa). Superconducting transition temperature $T_c \approx 261$ K. **b)** sample synthesized with Sr- Ca-Li (1:2:20) alloy at $T = 623$ K for 1 minute. Begin of high- T_c transition is smeared between $T_{onset} \approx 273$ K and $T_c \approx 267$ K. **c)** sample synthesized with Sr- Ca-Li (1:2:20) alloy at 473 K for 10 minutes. Magnetization data demonstrate the superconducting transition at ${}^2T_c > 350$ K with a preceding step at ${}^1T_c \approx 290$ K, which may indicate the inhomogeneity of the superconducting phase(s). Applied magnetic fields were perpendicular to carbon layers in samples. Measurement data points from zero-field cooling (ZFC) and field-cooling (FC) modes (filled/open circles); connecting lines to guide the eye.

S.4.4 Ferromagnetic reference sample of FeF₃

Figure S17. Temperature dependence of the remanent magnetization of weak ferromagnetic FeF₃ sample. After ZFC cooling a remanent magnetization was created by application and subsequent switching of magnetic field of 1 T at $T = 5.2$ K. At Heating 1 run the sample was heated to $T = 130$ K. At reverse Cooling 2 run the sample was cooled down to ca. 11 K and again heated to $T = 360$ K (Heating 3 run).

S.4.5 Magnetic field dependence of transitions in graphite intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy

Figure S18. Magnetic field dependence of transitions in graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIb): temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, measured in ZFC and FC modes at different applied magnetic fields in two orientations: **a)** parallel to carbon layers; and **b)** perpendicular to carbon layers.

Figure S19. Magnetic field dependence of transitions in graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIc): **a)** $m(T)$ data measured in ZFC and FC modes at different magnetic fields applied perpendicular to carbon layers. In contrast to the Sample IIIb, this sample does not show the superconducting transition at low temperatures due to $\text{CaC}_6/\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$ impurity phase. **b)** Magnetic field dependence of the magnetization change $|\Delta m|$ during the high- T_c transition. Panel **c)** shows the magnetic field induced shift of the transition onset temperature T_c . Blue dotted lines are guides for eye.

S.4.6 Magnetic field dependence of transition temperature

Figure S20. Magnetic field dependence of the transition temperature T_c and magnetization in a graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIb). Magnetization measured in magnetic field parallel to carbon layers at $T = 290$ K (magenta diamonds) with fit curve (dashed magenta line) according to the Eq. 1. Magnetic field dependence of the transition temperature T_c (red and black points) at magnetic fields parallel (red points) and perpendicular (black points) to carbon layers. Dashed blue line is a fit based on the Eq. 2.

Figure S20 shows magnetic field dependence of the transition temperature T_c and magnetization m in a graphite sample intercalated with ternary Sr-Ca-Li alloy (Sample IIIb). The magnetization is measured at $T = 290$ K as a function of magnetic field strength in parallel to the carbon layers. After an initial strong increase with the external magnetic field, the measured magnetization of the sample saturates above ~ 0.3 T, which coincides with the flattening of T_c above 0.2 T.

The magnetization m due to the polarization of the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ conducting electrons in the external field H is described by the expression

$$m = N\mu_B \tanh\left(\frac{\mu_B H}{k_B T}\right) \quad (1)$$

where N is the amount of conducting electrons, μ_B and k_B are the Bohr magneton and the Boltzmann constant. A fit of expression (1) to the magnetization data for Sample IIIb reflects the experimental features described above.

As shown in Fig. S20, the magnetic field dependence of T_c demonstrates a similar trend: it is strong below and saturates above ~ 0.3 T. A fit of experimental data $T_c(H)$ based on similar to expression 1 functional dependence

$$T_c(H) = P1 * \tanh(H * P2) + P3 \quad (2)$$

supports the relevance of Pauli paramagnetism for the observed magnetic field dependence of T_c . The fit parameters $P1 = -19(1)$, $P2 = 4,6(6)$, $P3 = 266,2(9)$.

S.4.7 Estimation of high- T_c fraction

To determine an absolute superconducting fraction in novel high-temperature graphite-based superconductors we compared their susceptibility $dm(H)/dH$ with a susceptibility of the high-purity lead (99.9999%) of equal size and therefore with the same demagnetizing factor. Magnetization measurements of superconducting lead were done at 4.2 K. At this temperature, we observe a linear increase in its negative magnetization with increasing magnetic field until to the transition in the normal state. Apparently, also only range with a linear dependence of $m(H)$ magnetization below the penetration field H_p has been considered for intercalated compounds (Fig. 5d of the main text).

S.4.8 Magnetic properties of Sample III d used in electrical resistance measurements

Sample III d was synthesized with ternary Sr- Ca-Li (1:2:20) alloy at 423 K for 10 minutes. Temperature behavior of trapped flux generated at $\mu_0 H_M = 1$ T and $T_M = 5.2$ K indicates high- T_c transition near 350 K (Fig. 6b of the main text). Temperature-dependent magnetization measurements of this sample are presented in Fig. S21.

Figure S21. Temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of Sample III d used in electrical resistance measurements. ZFC-FC measurements are done in different magnetic fields perpendicular to carbon layers.

S.4.9 HOPG samples intercalated by ternary Sr–Ca–Li alloy

Figure S22. Temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of HOPG samples. HOPG intercalated by ternary Sr–Ca–Li alloy (atomic ratio 1:2:20) for 1 minute at 473 K (green points), 523 K (red points), 573 K (blue points) and 623 K (black points). ZFC–FC measurements are done in magnetic field of 6 mT. The low- T_c transition near 11.5 K attributed to known superconducting phases of CaC_6 or $\text{Ca}_2\text{Li}_3\text{C}_6$. The high- T_c transition around room temperature is significantly smeared.

S.4.10 Samples intercalated with other alloys: K–Li, Sr–Li, Mg–Li, Zn–Li, and Mg–Zn–Li

Figure S23. Temperature-dependent magnetization, $m(T)$, of graphite samples intercalated with K–Li, Sr–Li, Mg–Li, Zn–Li, and Mg–Zn–Li alloys. **a)** sample synthesized with K–Li (1:3, 523 K, 30 seconds); high- T_c transition at ≈ 240 K. **b)** sample synthesized with Sr–Li (1:3, 623 K, 60 seconds); high- T_c transition at ≈ 242 K. **c)** sample synthesized with Mg–Li (1:4, 623 K, 5 minutes); high- T_c transition at ≈ 264 K. **d)** sample synthesized with Zn–Li (1:4, 573 K, 5 minutes); high- T_c transition at ≈ 270 K. **e)** sample synthesized with Mg–Zn–Li (1:1:8, 523 K, 4 minutes); high- T_c transition at ≈ 300 K. Applied magnetic fields were perpendicular to carbon layers in the samples.

Figure S24. Magnetic field dependence of superconducting transitions in graphite samples intercalated with Mg–Li alloy. The sample was synthesized with Mg–Li (1:4) alloy at 523 K for 5 minutes. **a)** Temperature dependence of magnetization $m(T)$ at different magnetic fields H_{appl} applied perpendicular to carbon layers. **b)** Magnetic field dependence of the magnetization change $|\Delta m|$ during the high- T_c transition. **c)** Shift of the transition temperature T_c in applied magnetic fields.

Figure S25. Magnetic field dependence of superconducting transitions in graphite samples intercalated with Zn–Li alloy. The sample was synthesized with Zn–Li (1:4) alloy at 573 K for 5 minutes. **a)** Temperature dependence of magnetization $m(T)$ at different magnetic fields H_{appl} applied perpendicular to carbon layers. **b)** Magnetic field dependence of the magnetization change $|\Delta m|$ during the high- T_c transition. **c)** Shift of the transition temperature T_c in applied magnetic fields.

References [35 – 41] from the SI are co-listed with other references in the main manuscript.